

If You Want Peace, War and Preparation for War Are Poor Decisions

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1. Introduction

Direct violence can occur at a number of levels. Violence occurring during wartime is an obvious example, but inter-personal violence also occurs in the form of corporal punishment in homes and schools, intimate partner violence, wider gender-based violence and bullying in schools and workplaces. This violence is not only physical, and can take verbal, psychological and economic forms. Inter-communal violence is often based on tribal, cultural, language and religious differences, and may morph into civil war and possibly to war between countries; although the latter has been rare in its pure form for many decades. As an aside, it is worth noting that deaths from inter-personal violence in Africa, and its economic costs, are far higher than those resulting from war (Harris, 2024). This follows from the fact that violence in homes, for example, occurs in many households throughout the continent every day of the year; whereas civil wars, while often brutal, are often short term in duration and are concentrated in specific areas.

There is a widespread belief that violence works. For example, it is commonly held that corporal punishment results in 'good' children, 'getting tough on crime' deters criminality, and war deals with the matter quickly and results in peace. But does violence work? This article examines the evidence with particular reference to war, while noting that similar investigations have been carried out for the other forms of violence mentioned above (e.g. Harris, 2019).

To summarize the approach which follows, we examine the case for and against war under five headings - individual ethics, international law, cost, effectiveness and the availability of alternatives. This discussion initially focusses on war itself and not on the preparation for war by countries in the form of military forces; this second issue is discussed separately in section 3.

2. Five reasons why war is a poor decision

War violates individual ethics

‘Treat other people the way you would like them to treat you’, and its negative equivalent, are golden threads running through all religious traditions. For a short but elegant exposition of the golden rule and its close relative, compassion, see Armstrong (2009). Deep down, the vast majority of individuals know that violence is wrong, especially that involving interpersonal violence. But individuals can be brainwashed into thinking that there is no alternative to violence when it comes to groups or countries which have been defined as enemies. This brainwashing is often based on beliefs and assumptions which are questionable, including the belief that there is no alternative to violence. In fact, there are always alternatives and violence is only one of the choices we have open to us.

But can personal ethics apply to the actions of a state? One insightful response to this question concerns the bombardment of Alexandria by British naval forces in 1882, after which a prominent member of parliament, John Bright, resigned from the government with the following words:

The House [of Commons] knows that for forty years at least I have endeavoured to teach my countrymen an opinion and doctrine which I hold, namely, that the moral law is intended not for individual life only, but for the life and practice of States in their dealing with one another. I think that in the present case there has been a manifest violation both of International Law and of the moral law, and therefore it is impossible for me to give my support to it.

War violates international law

The United Nations Charter on which international law is based states the purposes of the UN (with emphasis added) as being:

To maintain international peace and security, and to that end: to take effective collective measures for the prevention and removal of threats to the peace, and for the suppression of acts of aggression or other breaches of the peace, and to *bring about by peaceful means*, and in conformity with the principles of justice and international law, adjustment or settlement of international disputes or situations which might lead to a breach of the peace ...

[and that the following principles are to be followed]:

All Members shall *settle their international disputes by peaceful means* in such a manner that international peace and security, and justice, are not endangered.

All Members *shall refrain in their international relations from the threat or use of force* against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state, or in any other manner inconsistent with the Purposes of the United Nations.

From the above, international law is clear: differences between countries must be settled using nonviolent means. Of course, reality can be complex, including what to do with states or groups within states which refuse to obey international law. What nonviolent or less violent methods like economic sanctions might be used to change their behaviour and is the use of military force against them justifiable if these efforts do not succeed?

War has huge costs

Two current examples illustrate the costs which wars involve. The war in Sudan is a power struggle between the Sudanese army and the Rapid Support Forces which began in April 2023. By June 2024, at least 15,500 people, mostly civilians, had been killed, over six million displaced and over 25 million pushed into acute hunger as a result of war. Despite this massive suffering, there is no end in sight. In July 2024, Firmian (2024) asserted that ‘The prospects for a peaceful resolution to Sudan’s conflict... appear bleak. Even a temporary ceasefire to facilitate humanitarian aid remains improbable. The United Nations Security Council remains deeply divided on ways forward and the African Union has yet to propose a workable plan’.

The current war in Gaza began when Hamas fighters attacked Israeli settlements on October 7, 2023, killing 764 civilians and 373 security personnel and taking around 240 hostages. Israel immediately began bombing Gaza. By June 19, 2024, 37,396 people had been killed, according to data provided by the Gaza Health Ministry, based on deaths in its hospitals or on bodies brought in dead, with identification. The majority of those killed have been women and children. Perhaps three times as many have been wounded, many of whom are permanently disabled, and at least 10,000 more dead are estimated to be buried under rubble. When indirect deaths resulting from damage/destruction of the health care infrastructure, severe shortages of food, water and shelter, and the obstruction of humanitarian organization work are included, a conservative estimate of deaths due to the war is 186,000, some 7.9 per cent of the population (Khatib et al., 2024). These short-term casualties are only part of the human costs. The physical and emotional trauma caused to Gaza’s two million people are incalculable and will last for generations.

Then there is physical damage of the war – the destruction of houses, hospitals and schools and the damage to water and sanitation, electricity and transport infrastructures. In April 2024, the cost of damage to critical infrastructure in Gaza was estimated at around \$18.5 billion, equivalent to 97 per cent of the combined GDP of the West Bank and Gaza in 2022 (World Bank and United Nations, 2024). It has been estimated that it will take up to fifteen years to clear the 40 million tons of war rubble (Al Jazeera, 2024).

Furthermore, violence begets more violence. There has been a dramatic increase in violence in the West Bank, including East Jerusalem, since the war in Gaza started, as Israeli settlers have increased their efforts to take over Palestinian land by violence. This has resulted in the deaths of 521 Palestinians, including 126 children, between 7 October 2023 and 10 June 2024. Over 5,200 people, 800 of them children, have been injured (World Health Organisation, 2024).

After many months of relentless attacks by one of the world's most sophisticated military forces using weaponry supplied by the US, and despite the immense suffering of the civilian population, there is no end in sight to the war in Gaza. This accords with the outcomes of many bombing campaigns, including the German blitz on Britain and the subsequent allied bombing of Germany during the second world war and the bombing of Vietnam and neighbouring countries during the Vietnam war. These campaigns killed massive numbers of civilians and some combatants but did not cause the civilian populations to give up or to overthrow their governments; rather, it hardened their resolve to resist their attackers. This seems to be happening in Gaza and most analysts believe that a new generation of enemies of Israel will be created as a result of its disproportionate and genocidal response to the October 7 attacks.

War is not effective in bringing about sustainable peace

War may be costly in human and physical terms, but doesn't it help to build a 'sustained and democratic peace'? In fact, the track record of war shows that it is rarely effective in this regard. The outcome of many wars is negative peace, where fighting may stop but the underlying issues remain unresolved; as a result, the peace is fragile. Past examples include Korea (1950-53), Vietnam (1955-75), Iran-Iraq (1980-88), Iraq (2003-11), Libya (2014-20), and Afghanistan (2001-21). Current examples include Syria, Ukraine, Gaza, Sudan and DR Congo.

Recent studies of US military interventions aimed at bringing about regime change have found that 'these rarely succeed regardless of the strategy utilized and... often produce unintended consequences, such as humanitarian crises and weaker internal security within the targeted state' (Denison, 2020, p.3). A similar conclusion was reached by Toft and Kushi (2023), using the comprehensive Military Intervention Project database. The global 'war on terror' declared by the US in response to the 9/11 attacks – the centrepiece of which was the invasion of Iraq – has cost hundreds of thousands of lives, brought al-Qaida into places where it did not previously exist, led to the formation of Islamic State and resulted in much greater instability in the Middle East.

There are nonviolent alternatives to war

It is difficult to know what would have happened if the wars listed above had not taken place but there is relevant evidence on the effectiveness of nonviolent campaigns in bringing about social change. The range of nonviolent methods available is formidable, on which see the classic list of 198 methods documented by Gene Sharp (1973).

Methodologically, it is not enough to use successful nonviolent campaigns as a measure of their effectiveness because there are also many undocumented failures. Fortunately, a remarkable study by Chenoweth and Stephan (2011) overcame this methodological problem by examining 323 violent and nonviolent campaigns between 1900 and 2006 involving big issues – regime change, anti-occupation and secession. They found that violent campaigns were fully or partially successful in 26 per cent of cases while for nonviolent campaigns, the figure was 53 per cent. They suggested that the greater effectiveness of nonviolent campaigns was because many more people were able to participate in nonviolent as opposed to violent campaigns and the withdrawal of support of those in power was therefore far greater:

When people refuse their cooperation, withhold their help, and persist in their disobedience and defiance, they are denying their opponent the basic human assistance and cooperation which any government hierarchical system requires. If they do this *in sufficient numbers for long enough*, that government or hierarchical system will no longer have power.

(Sharp, 1973, p,64, [emphasis added])

They also found that nonviolent campaigns were more likely to result in a ‘sustained and democratic peace’:

Holding other variables constant, the probability that a country will be a democracy five years after a campaign is 57 per cent among successful nonviolent campaigns but less than 6 per cent for successful violent campaigns.

(Chenoweth and Stephan, 2011, p.213 and p.215)

In summary, these five points provide a formidable argument against the use of war to bring about peace. They justify a reallocation of government resources away from the military towards more cost-effective peacebuilding activities, as explained by International Alert (2017). The fact that war continues to be a major option for so many countries shows high levels of ignorance and a lack of imagination on the part of military and political leadership and the intertwining of military and political power.

3.Preparing for war is also a poor decision

Even if actually engaging in war is a poor decision, might not a strong military deter other countries from invading, and groups within the country from trying to take over control? This is the deterrence argument – that if you want peace, you need to prepare for war.

In a somewhat dated study, Collier and Hoeffler (2002) found that there was no relationship between the military expenditure of 161 countries between 1960 and 1990 and the likelihood of their involvement in wars. In their words, ‘Because [military] spending is

so closely matched by neighbors, an increase in military spending by one country has little effect on its external security. Further, it has no discernible effect on deterring internal insecurity' (2002, p.7). There is no obvious reason why this finding would have changed in more recent years. That is, high levels of military expenditure do not protect countries from civil wars and low levels do not make it more likely. While this argument applies in general, there may be countries with specific security challenges which lead them to regard a large military as a necessity.

It is important to recognize that having a military is a choice, much like having a national airline or a national shipping fleet. A number of countries, many but not all small island countries like Mauritius, have made the choice not to have a military (Barany, 2023) or, in some cases, to disband the military they previously had. There are other reasons for having small militaries or having no military at all. First, many militaries engage in human rights abuses, often against opponents of the ruling party. Second, militaries may engage in coups to overthrow elected governments. Third, civilian agencies can carry out many of the functions of the military and can do so more cost effectively. Finally, there is the opportunity cost argument that resources allocated to the military mean that less is available for other categories of expenditure. Most of the discussion of the opportunity costs of military expenditure concerns the foregone opportunities to spend on areas like health and education, which have obvious economic outcomes for citizens in ways that military expenditure does not:

Whatever else can be said for it, military activity does not grow food, it does not produce clothing, it does not build housing, and it does not keep people amused. Nor does it create the kind of machinery, equipment and facilities that can be used to [produce such goods and services]. Military activity may have other kinds of value, but it has no *economic* value because it does not directly continue to material well being...

(Dumas 2002, pp.16-17)

More recently, in the context of the existential threat of climate change, the increase of military expenditures following the Russian invasion of Ukraine has meant reduced allocations to mitigating climate change and to compensating those countries most impacted by it (Transnational Institute, Tipping Point North South and Stop Wapenhandel, 2024).

4. So if we aspire to be peacemakers and peacebuilders, what can we do?

Using the well-known words of the UNESCO charter, since wars begin in the minds of men, we have to work on changing those minds including, perhaps, our own. Below are five changes which need to become widely accepted.

- ◆ We need to recognize that violence is not an inevitable response to a dispute but is always a choice.
- ◆ We need to build competence in the skills of conflict resolution and mediation in ourselves and in others.
- ◆ We need to study the methods and track record of nonviolence.
- ◆ We need to work, with others, to plan and implement nonviolent action to bring about change.
- ◆ We need to be in it for the long haul – for as long as it takes.

In 1950, Ralph Bunche became the first African-American to receive the Nobel Peace Prize for his work in the late 1940s as a United Nations mediator in the Palestine conflict. He called himself 'an incurable optimist' and his words can encourage us in a particularly violent time in recent history:

There are some in the world who are prematurely resigned to the inevitability of war. Among them are the advocates of 'preventive war', who in their resignation to war, wish merely to select their own time initiating it. To suggest that war can prevent war is a base play on words and a despicable form of warmongering. The objective of any who sincerely believe in peace clearly must be to exhaust every honourable recourse in the effort to save the peace.

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